

Machine Learning for Student Dropout Prediction in Higher
Education: A Systematic Review
Supplementary Material: Tables of Retrieved References

Catharin, L. G.¹, Bravin, C. E. P.¹, Silva, E. B.¹
Teixeira, L. O.¹, Colanzi, T. E.¹, Costa, Y. M. G.¹
Feltrim, V. D.¹

¹State University of Maringá (UEM), Brazil

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Table 1: List of Publications Included in the SRL (Springer)

Authors	Title	Year
Forti, M. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Dropout from Higher Education with Multinomial Finite Mixture Models: Empirical Evidence from Italy	2025
Cechinel, C. <i>et al.</i>	LANSE: A Cloud-Powered Learning Analytics Platform for the Automated Identification of Students at Risk in Learning Management Systems	2024
Bognár, L.	Predicting Student Attrition in University Courses	2024
Forero, L. <i>et al.</i>	Machine Learning for the Identification of Students at Risk of Academic Desertion	2019
Sarra, A. <i>et al.</i>	Identifying Students at Risk of Academic Failure Within the Educational Data Mining Framework	2019
Xu, W. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Analytics for Tertiary Learners in New Zealand Who Are at Risk of Dropping Out of Education	2019

Table 2: List of Publications Included in the SLR (SciELO)

Authors	Title / <i>Free translation into English, when applicable</i>	Year
Villa-Murillo, A.	A methodological proposal to address the academic dropout phenomenon based on an intelligent prediction model: a case study	2024
Lopes, R. <i>et al.</i>	Fatores associados à evasão de calouros no ensino superior: um estudo com dados da Universidade Federal do Recôncavo da Bahia / <i>Factors associated with freshman dropout in higher education: a study using data from the Federal University of the Recôncavo da Bahia</i>	2023
Bitencourt, W. <i>et al.</i>	Pode a inteligência artificial apoiar ações contra evasão escolar universitária? / <i>Can artificial intelligence support actions to prevent university student dropout?</i>	2022
Pérez, A. <i>et al.</i>	Prediction model of first-year student desertion at Universidad Bernardo O'Higgins (UBO)	2018
Durso, S. <i>et al.</i>	Determinant Factors for Undergraduate Student's Dropout in an Accounting Studies Department of a Brazilian Public University	2018
Sousa, A. <i>et al.</i>	Utilização do sucesso acadêmico para prever o abandono escolar de estudantes do ensino superior: um caso de estudo / <i>Using academic success to predict higher education student dropout: a case study</i>	2018

Table 3: List of Publications Included in the SLR (ACM)

Authors	Title	Year
Lopez, J. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Analysis of Student Dropout in Higher Education	2025
Blazkova, T. <i>et al.</i>	Fairness Over Time: A Nationwide Study of Evolving Bias in Dropout Prediction	2025
Yao, C. <i>et al.</i>	Towards Fair and Privacy-Aware Transfer Learning for Educational Predictive Modeling: A Case Study on Retention Prediction in Community Colleges	2025
Glandorf, D. <i>et al.</i>	Temporal and Between-Group Variability in College Dropout Prediction	2024
Romsaiyud, W. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Modeling of Student Dropout Using Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets and XGBoost in Open University	2024
Riello, P. <i>et al.</i>	Reimagining Student Success Prediction: Applying LLMs in Educational AI with XAI	2024
Poellhuber, L.-V. <i>et al.</i>	Cluster-Based Performance of Student Dropout Prediction as a Solution for Large Scale Models in a Moodle LMS	2023
Cruz, R. C. <i>et al.</i>	A Score approach to identify the risk of students dropout: an experiment with Information Systems Course	2023
Quille, K. <i>et al.</i>	Evolving Towards a Trustworthy AIEd Model to Predict at Risk Students in Introductory Programming Courses	2023
Koutcheme, C. <i>et al.</i>	Methodological Considerations for Predicting At-risk Students	2022
Yu, R. <i>et al.</i>	Should College Dropout Prediction Models Include Protected Attributes?	2021
Meca, I. <i>et al.</i>	Early Warning Methodology for dropping out of university degrees	2021
Baranyi, M. <i>et al.</i>	Interpretable Deep Learning for University Dropout Prediction	2020
Shiau, Y.	University Dropout Prevention through the Application of Big Data	2020
Ajoodha, R. <i>et al.</i>	Forecasting Learner Attrition for Student Success at a South African University	2020
Manrique, R. <i>et al.</i>	An Analysis of Student Representation, Representative Features and Classification Algorithms to Predict Degree Dropout	2019
Chen, Y. <i>et al.</i>	Running out of STEM: A Comparative Study across STEM Majors of College Students At-Risk of Dropping Out Early	2018
Kang, K. and Wang, S.	Analyze and Predict Student Dropout from Online Programs	2018
Ameri, S. <i>et al.</i>	Survival Analysis based Framework for Early Prediction of Student Dropouts	2016
Kostopoulos, G. <i>et al.</i>	Estimating Student Dropout in Distance Higher Education Using Semi-Supervised Techniques	2015
Datta, S. and Mengel, S.	Multi-stage decision method to generate rules for student retention	2015

Table 4: List of Publications Included in the SLR (SBC)

Authors	Title / <i>Free translation into English, when applicable</i>	Year
Rodrigues, H. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Models for University Dropout at UNIRIO	2025
Pereira, F. <i>et al.</i>	Big Data na Educação: Predição de Evasão Estudantil com Aprendizado de Máquina / <i>Big Data in Education: Predicting Student Dropout with Machine Learning</i>	2025
Souza, L. <i>et al.</i>	Aplicação de uma metodologia de previsão de evasão: um estudo de caso no campus UFV-Florestal / <i>Application of a dropout prediction methodology: a case study at the UFV-Florestal campus</i>	2025
Bezerra, W. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Student Dropout Rates at Higher Degree Using Machine Learning and Dimensionality Reduction	2025
Rodrigues, H. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Student Dropout on the Information Systems Undergraduate Program of UNIRIO Using Decision Tree	2024
Freire, J. <i>et al.</i>	Modelo para previsão precoce de abandono de uma disciplina de introdução à programação / <i>Model for early prediction of dropout in an introductory programming course</i>	2024
Oliveira, R. <i>et al.</i>	Modelo de Predição de Evasão Escolar com Base em Dados de Autoavaliação de Cursos de Graduação / <i>Student Dropout Prediction Model Based on Self-Assessment Data from Undergraduate Programs</i>	2024
Carvalho, C. <i>et al.</i>	Avaliação da interpretabilidade de modelos por meio da clusterização de explicações no contexto da predição de evasão no ensino superior / <i>Evaluating model interpretability through clustering of explanations in the context of higher education dropout prediction</i>	2023
Kantorski, G. <i>et al.</i>	Mineração de Dados Educacionais para Predição da Evasão em Cursos de Graduação Presenciais no Ensino Superior / <i>Educational Data Mining for Predicting Dropout in On-Campus Undergraduate Programs in Higher Education</i>	2023
Van Vossen, L. <i>et al.</i>	Dropoutless: plataforma colaborativa de predição de evasão / <i>Dropoutless: a collaborative dropout prediction platform</i>	2023
Melo, E. <i>et al.</i>	Improving the prediction of school dropout with the support of the semi-supervised learning approach	2023
Costa, H. <i>et al.</i>	A Framework for prediction of dropout in distance learning through XAI techniques in Virtual Learning Environment	2022
Viana, F. <i>et al.</i>	Avaliação de Classificadores para Predição de Evasão no Ensino Superior Utilizando Janela Semestral / <i>Evaluation of Classifiers for Predicting Dropout in Higher Education Using a Semester-Based Window</i>	2022
Colpo, M. <i>et al.</i>	Predição da evasão estudantil: uma análise comparativa de diferentes representações de treino na aprendizagem de modelos genéricos / <i>Student dropout prediction: a comparative analysis of different training representations in learning generic models</i>	2021
Jesus, H. <i>et al.</i>	Predição de Evasão Escolar na Licenciatura em Computação / <i>Prediction of Student Dropout in the Computer Science Teaching Degree Program</i>	2021
Santos, C. <i>et al.</i>	É Possível Prever Evasão com Base Apenas no Desempenho Acadêmico? / <i>Is It Possible to Predict Dropout Based Solely on Academic Performance?</i>	2021
Hortêncio Filho, F. <i>et al.</i>	Predição de Evasão Utilizando Técnicas de Classificação: Um Estudo de Caso do Instituto Federal do Ceará / <i>Dropout Prediction Using Classification Techniques: A Case Study of the Federal Institute of Ceará</i>	2020
Hortêncio Filho, F. <i>et al.</i>	Análise de Classificadores para Predição de Evasão de Campi de uma Instituição de Ensino Federal / <i>Analysis of Classifiers for Predicting Dropout Across Campuses of a Federal Educational Institution</i>	2020
Silva, D. <i>et al.</i>	Minerando Dados de um Juiz On-line para Prever a Evasão de Estudantes em Disciplinas Introdutórias de Programação / <i>Mining Data from an Online Judge to Predict Student Dropout in Introductory Programming Courses</i>	2020
Brito, B. <i>et al.</i>	Identificação de Atributos Relevantes na Evasão no Ensino Superior Público Brasileiro / <i>Identification of Relevant Attributes in Dropout in Brazilian Public Higher Education</i>	2020
Teodoro, L. <i>et al.</i>	Machine Learning Applied to Academic Drop Out Prediction in Brazilian Public Universities	2020
Sales, A. <i>et al.</i>	Exploiting Academic Records for Predicting Student Drop Out: a case study in Brazilian higher education	2016

Table 5: List of Publications Included in the SLR (CAPES)

Authors	Title / <i>Free translation into English, when applicable</i>	Year
Silva, R. <i>et al.</i>	Modelagem preditiva para sucesso acadêmico: um estudo de caso em um curso de ciência da computação / <i>Predictive Modeling for Academic Success: a Case Study in a Computer Science Program</i>	2025
Juliani, J.	Predição de Evasão em Cursos EAD: um Modelo Baseado em Árvore de Decisão que Integra Causas Exógenas e Endógenas/ <i>Dropout Prediction in Distance Education Courses: a Decision Tree-Based Model Integrating Exogenous and Endogenous Factors</i>	2025
Sousa, F. <i>et al.</i>	Análise de Classificadores para Predição de Evasão em um Curso Superior de Tecnologia da Informação de um Instituto Federal / <i>Analysis of Classifiers for Predicting Dropout in an Information Technology Higher Education Program at a Federal Institute</i>	2025
Sosa-Alonso, J. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting university dropout: connecting big data and structural models	2025
Kowarsch, D.	Elevating Student Success: Harnessing Machine Learning to Enhance University Completion Rates	2025
Menolli, A. <i>et al.</i>	Exploring Feature Reduction for Dropout Predicting in Higher Education in Brazil	2025
Delogu, M. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting dropout from higher education: Evidence from Italy	2024
Diaz Lema, M. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting dropout in Higher Education across borders	2024
Rabelo, A. and Zárate, L.	A Model for Predicting Dropout of Higher Education Students	2024
Vaarma, M. and Li, H.	Predicting student dropouts with machine learning: An empirical study in Finnish higher education	2024
Seo, E. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive modelling of student dropout risk: Practical insights from a South Korean distance university	2024
Charitaki, G. <i>et al.</i>	A nonlinear state space model predicting dropout: the case of special education students in the Hellenic Open University	2024
Delen, D. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting and Mitigating Freshmen Student Attrition: A Local-Explainable Machine Learning Framework	2024
Arthana, I. <i>et al.</i>	Optimizing Dropout Prediction in University Using Oversampling Techniques for Imbalanced Datasets	2024
Gonzalez-Nucamendi, A. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive analytics study to determine undergraduate students at risk of dropout	2023
Hoyos Osorio, J. and Santacoloma, G.	Predictive Model to Identify College Students with High Dropout Rates	2023
Huo, H. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Dropout for Nontraditional Undergraduate Students: A Machine Learning Approach	2023
Villa-Murillo, A. <i>et al.</i>	A methodological proposal to address the academic dropout phenomenon based on an intelligent prediction model: a case study	2023
Bañeres, D. <i>et al.</i>	An early warning system to identify and intervene online dropout learners	2023
Huynh-Cam, T. <i>et al.</i>	Early prediction models and crucial factor extraction for first-year undergraduate student dropouts	2023
Kamakshamma, V. <i>et al.</i>	Adaptive-CSSA: adaptive-chicken squirrel search algorithm driven deep belief network for student stress-level and drop out prediction with MapReduce framework	2023
Phan, M. <i>et al.</i>	A Decision Support Framework to Incorporate Textual Data for Early Student Dropout Prediction in Higher Education	2022
Lizarte Simón, E. and Puerta, J.	Prediction of early dropout in higher education using the SCPQ	2022
Santos, J. <i>et al.</i>	Aplicando Mineração de Dados Para Predição da Evasão Escolar no Ensino Superior em uma Instituição Federal de Ensino / <i>Applying Data Mining to Predict Student Dropout in Higher Education at a Federal Educational Institution</i>	2022
Mubarak, A. <i>et al.</i>	Prediction of students' early dropout based on their interaction logs in online learning environment	2022
Barramuño, M. <i>et al.</i>	Prediction of student attrition risk using machine learning	2022
Urbina-Nájera, A. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Model for Taking Decision to Prevent University Dropout	2022
Pei, B. and Xing, W.	An Interpretable Pipeline for Identifying At-Risk Students	2022
Cannistrà, M. <i>et al.</i>	Early-predicting dropout of university students: an application of innovative multi-level machine learning and statistical techniques	2022
Rosa, C. <i>et al.</i>	A predição da formatura e da evasão em uma universidade pública a partir de um modelo logístico / <i>The Prediction of Graduation and Dropout in a Public University Using a Logistic Model</i>	2021
von Hippel, P. <i>et al.</i>	The data revolution comes to higher education: Identifying students at risk of dropout in Chile	2021
Amare, M. <i>et al.</i>	Global challenges of students dropout: A prediction model development using machine learning algorithms on higher education datasets	2021
Csalódi, R. and Abonyi, J.	Integrated Survival Analysis and Frequent Pattern Mining for Course Failure-Based Prediction of Student Dropout	2021

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Table 5 (Continued from previous page)

Authors	Title	Year
Park, H. and Yoo, S.	Early Dropout Prediction in Online Learning of University using Machine Learning	2021
Karimi-Haghighi, M. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Early Dropout: Calibration and Algorithmic Fairness Considerations	2021
Ortiz-Lozano, J. <i>et al.</i>	University student retention: Best time and data to identify undergraduate students at risk of dropout	2020
Alvarez, N. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Computer Engineering Students' Dropout in Cuban Higher Education with Pre-enrollment and Early Performance Data	2020
Silva, F. <i>et al.</i>	Evasão ou Permanência? Modelos Preditivos para a Gestão do Ensino Superior / <i>Dropout or Persistence? Predictive Models for Higher Education Management</i>	2020
Nicoletti, M. <i>et al.</i>	A Machine Learning-Based Computational System Proposal Aiming at Higher Education Dropout Prediction	2020
Delen, D. <i>et al.</i>	Development of a Bayesian Belief Network-based DSS for predicting and understanding freshmen student attrition	2020
Urbina-Nájera, A. <i>et al.</i>	University dropout: Patterns to prevent it by applying educational data mining	2020
Agrusti, F. <i>et al.</i>	Deep learning approach for predicting university dropout: A case study at Roma Tre University	2020
Korhonen, V. and Rautopuro, J.	Identifying Problematic Study Progression and "At-Risk" Students in Higher Education in Finland	2019
Lacave, C. <i>et al.</i>	Learning Analytics to identify dropout factors of Computer Science studies through Bayesian networks	2018
Aulck, L. <i>et al.</i>	STEM-ming the Tide: Predicting STEM attrition using student transcript data	2017
Aulck, L. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Student Dropout in Higher Education	2016
Sivakumar, S. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Modeling of Student Dropout Indicators in Educational Data Mining using Improved Decision Tree	2016
Lourens, A. and Bleazard, D.	Applying Predictive Analytics in Identifying Students at Risk: A Case Study	2016
Saranya, A. and Rajeswari, J.	Enhanced Prediction of Student Dropouts Using Fuzzy Inference System and Logistic Regression	2016
Detoni, D. <i>et al.</i>	Aprendendo a Identificar Estudantes em Risco em Educação a Distância Usando Contagem de Interações / <i>Learning to Identify At-Risk Students in Distance Education Using Interaction Counts</i>	2016
Cambruzzi, W. <i>et al.</i>	Dropout Prediction and Reduction in Distance Education Courses with the Learning Analytics Multitrail Approach	2015
Chai, K. and Gibson, D.	Predicting the Risk of Attrition for Undergraduate Students with Time Based Modelling	2015

Table 6: List of Publications Included in the SLR (IEEE)

Authors	Title / <i>Free translation into English, when applicable</i>	Year
Hoang, N. L. T. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Modeling of Higher Education Dropout Using Deep Neural Network	2025
Malkanathi, C. <i>et al.</i>	TabNet-Based Multi-Class Prediction Model for Student Dropout and Academic Performance in Higher Education	2025
Posadas, M. F. E. <i>et al.</i>	Early Predictive Modeling of Engineering Student Attrition: An AI-Driven Machine Learning Approach	2025
Joshi, A. <i>et al.</i>	Towards a Student Dropout Prediction in Higher Education Institutions Using a Fuzzy RBF Approach	2025
Anik, M. S. M. <i>et al.</i>	Dropout Prediction of University Students in Bangladesh Using Machine Learning Technique	2025
Gorshkov, S. S. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Student Dropout Through Text and Media Content Analysis of VKontakte Profiles	2025
Balraj, E. <i>et al.</i>	A Simple Framework for Predicting Student Dropout Analysis Using Data Mining Algorithms	2025
Namitha, T. N. <i>et al.</i>	AI-Powered Student Dropout Prediction Using AutoGluon FT-Transformer	2025
Cheng, Y.-H. <i>et al.</i>	Early Prediction of Student Suspension and Dropout for Counseling Resource Optimization Using Multilayer Perceptron	2025
Gilbert, J. <i>et al.</i>	A Prediction Model for At-Risk Students in Higher Education Institutions	2025
Castro, R. Q. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Modeling and Explainability for Academic Dropout Risk Detection Using Machine Learning	2025
Shrirao, V. <i>et al.</i>	Prediction Of Student Dropout Analysis For Education using Machine Learning	2025
Egoavil Cardenas, G. A. <i>et al.</i>	Building Generalizable Models for Student Retention: A Multi-Source Validation Framework for the Peruvian Higher Education Context	2025
Alvarenga, J. C. N. <i>et al.</i>	Predição de Evasão Escolar: Avaliação de Técnicas de Balanceamento Supervisionadas com Interpretação Local via LIME/ <i>Student Dropout Prediction: Evaluation of Supervised Balancing Techniques with Local Interpretation Using LIME</i>	2025
Lu, Y. <i>et al.</i>	Course-Level Clustering to Enhance Dropout Prediction Accuracy	2025
Mehedi, C. M. <i>et al.</i>	Smart Retention: AI-Driven Approaches for Predicting Student Dropouts in Higher Education in Bangladesh	2025
Aakool, A. A.-K. <i>et al.</i>	Early Detection of Student Dropout Indicators in Iraq Using Machine Learning Algorithms	2025
Hossain, M. <i>et al.</i>	Student Dropout Forecasting and Feature Analysis Through Machine Learning Algorithms	2025
Setiawan, R. <i>et al.</i>	Handling Class Imbalance in Student Success Prediction Using Machine Learning: A Comparison of SMOTE and SMOTETomek	2025
Pérez, M. <i>et al.</i>	Unlocking Student Success: Applying Machine Learning for Predicting Student Dropout in Higher Education	2025
Abdullah, A. <i>et al.</i>	Enhancing Student Retention: Predictive Machine Learning Models for Identifying and Preventing University Dropout	2025
Toirova, G. <i>et al.</i>	Machine Learning Models for Identifying At-Risk Students: Applications and Challenges in Higher Education	2025
Panizales, W. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Student Dropout Rates in Online Education Platforms Utilizing Naive Bayes Algorithm	2025
Budha, S. <i>et al.</i>	Hybrid Genetic Algorithm and Support Vector Machine for Prediction of Student Dropout and Success	2025
Karpagalakshmi, P. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting College Dropout Rates Using Machine Learning: A Student Success Initiative	2024
Zanellati, A. <i>et al.</i>	Balancing Performance and Explainability in Academic Dropout Prediction	2024
Brand, E. J. <i>et al.</i>	Toward Educational Sustainability: An AI System for Identifying and Preventing Student Dropout	2024
Padmasiri, P. <i>et al.</i>	Interpretable Prediction of Student Dropout Using Explainable AI Models	2024
Goran, R. <i>et al.</i>	Identifying and Understanding Student Dropouts Using Metaheuristic Optimized Classifiers and Explainable Artificial Intelligence Techniques	2024
Kumar, D. <i>et al.</i>	Random Forest Approach Optimized by the Grid Search Process for Predicting Dropout Students	2024
Gupta, K. <i>et al.</i>	Binary Classification of Students' Dropout Behaviour in Universities Using Machine Learning Algorithms	2024
Haque, M. R. <i>et al.</i>	Integrating Feature Selection and Extraction With Tuned Multilayer Perceptrons for Predicting Student Dropout Risk in Higher Education	2024
Kuntintara, W. <i>et al.</i>	Student Dropout Prediction Using Machine Learning	2024
Deb, S. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Student Dropout: A Machine Learning Approach	2024
Akter, T. <i>et al.</i>	Dropout Prediction of University Students in Bangladesh Using Machine Learning	2024
Durrani, U. <i>et al.</i>	Assessing the Effectiveness of Large Language Models in Predicting Student Dropout Rates	2024
Setiawan, I. <i>et al.</i>	Comparing Machine Learning Algorithms With Ensemble Model Using Random Oversampling for Predicting Student Dropouts	2024

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Table 6 (Continued from previous page)

Authors	Title	Year
Silpa, N. <i>et al.</i>	Fine-Tuning Student Success Prediction Through Ensemble Models Intertwined With Feature Engineering to Leverage Academic Interventions	2024
Al-Hammouri, M. F. <i>et al.</i>	Optimizing Multi-Class Classification in Educational Data With Ensemble Learning and Data Balancing Techniques	2024
Priya, G. V. <i>et al.</i>	Detecting and Predicting Learner's Dropout Using KNN Algorithm	2024
Fields, J. <i>et al.</i>	Integrating Categorical and Continuous Data in a Cluster-Then-Classify Methodology for Predicting Undergraduate Student Success	2024
Sabbir, W. <i>et al.</i>	Improving Predictive Analytics for Student Dropout: A Comprehensive Analysis and Model Evaluation	2024
Tenjo-Garcia, J. S. <i>et al.</i>	Analysis of Student Dropout in Industrial Engineering Students Using Computational Intelligence Techniques	2024
Abouelnour, S. <i>et al.</i>	Machine Learning in Higher Education: Predicting and Mitigating Student Dropout	2024
Andri <i>et al.</i>	Enhancing Student Dropout Prediction Using Chi-Square, SMOTE-ENN, and Hyperparameter Tuning of Random Forest	2024
Fernandes, T. <i>et al.</i>	Generating and Understanding Predictive Models for Student Attrition in Public Higher Education	2023
Prasanth, A. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Modeling of Student Behavior for Early Dropout Detection in Universities Using Machine Learning Techniques	2023
Davila, G. <i>et al.</i>	Student Dropout Prediction in High Education Using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Models: Case of Ecuadorian University	2023
Alruwais, N. M.	Deep FM-Based Predictive Model for Student Dropout in Online Classes	2023
Kendagor, V. J. <i>et al.</i>	A Convolutional Neural Network Framework for Predicting Student Dropout in Universities	2023
Jiménez, O. <i>et al.</i>	Model for the Prediction of Dropout in Higher Education in Peru applying Machine Learning Algorithms: Random Forest, Decision Tree, Neural Network and Support Vector Machine	2023
Almaazmi, A. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Student Dropout in Online Learning Platforms Using Deep Learning Techniques	2023
Andri <i>et al.</i>	Optimizing Random Forest Classification Using Chi-Square and SMOTE-ENN on Student Dropout Data	2023
Manir, S. B. <i>et al.</i>	Student Success Analysis for Minority Students in Higher Education	2023
Yusa, M. <i>et al.</i>	Combination of CRITIC and PROMETHEE II Methods as an Early Detection of Potential Dropout Students	2023
Anh, B. N. <i>et al.</i>	An University Student Dropout Detector Based on Academic Data	2023
Pratape, G. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Graduation and Dropout Rates: A Machine Learning Approach	2023
Karabacak, E. S. <i>et al.</i>	Comparison of Machine Learning Methods for Early Detection of Student Dropouts	2023
Lu, J. <i>et al.</i>	Interpretive Analyses of Learner Dropout Prediction in Online STEM Courses	2023
Tariq, A. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Early Withdrawal of University Students: A Comparative Study Between KNN and Decision Tree	2023
Nema, T. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Students' Academic Success Using Machine Learning Algorithms	2023
Lisboa, M. N. S. <i>et al.</i>	Study on Computer Science Undergraduate Students Dropout at the University of Brasília	2023
Singh, H. P. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Student-Teachers Dropout Risk and Early Identification: A Four-Step Logistic Regression Approach	2022
Hossain, M. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Analysis on University Dropout Rate of Bangladesh in COVID-19	2022
Coppo, E. C. <i>et al.</i>	Student Dropout Prediction Using 1D CNN-LSTM With Variational Autoencoder Oversampling	2022
Jawthari, M. <i>et al.</i>	Should Course-based At-risk Prediction Models Include Protected Features?	2022
Shynarbek, N. <i>et al.</i>	Forecasting Dropout in University Based on Students' Background Profile Data Through Automated Machine Learning Approach	2022
Deho, O. B. <i>et al.</i>	Should Learning Analytics Models Include Sensitive Attributes? Explaining the Why	2022
Shafiq, D. A. <i>et al.</i>	A Conceptual Predictive Analytics Model for the Identification of At-Risk Students in VLE Using Machine Learning Techniques	2022
Bassetti, E. <i>et al.</i>	ISIDE: Proactively Assist University Students at Risk of Dropout	2022
Mussida, P. <i>et al.</i>	A Computational Tool for Engineer Dropout Prediction	2022
Gupta, A. <i>et al.</i>	Mining Sequential Learning Trajectories With Hidden Markov Models for Early Prediction of At-Risk Students in E-Learning Environments	2022
Revathy, M. <i>et al.</i>	Machine Learning based Prediction of Dropout Students From the Education University Using SMOTE	2022
Fernández-García, A. J. <i>et al.</i>	A Real-Life Machine Learning Experience for Predicting University Dropout at Different Stages Using Academic Data	2021
Costa, A. G. <i>et al.</i>	Model for Prediction of Student Dropout in a Computer Science Course	2021
Gutierrez Pachas, D. A. <i>et al.</i>	A Comparative Study of WHO and WHEN Prediction Approaches for Early Identification of University Students at Dropout Risk	2021
Nasrullah, W. A. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Student's Failure in Education Based on Dropout Status	2021
Revathy, M. <i>et al.</i>	Collaborative learning for improving intellectual skills of dropout students using data mining techniques	2021

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Table 6 (Continued from previous page)

Authors	Title	Year
Uliyan, D. <i>et al.</i>	Deep Learning Model to Predict Students Retention Using BLSTM and CRF	2021
Fincham, E. <i>et al.</i>	Persistence and Performance in Co-Enrollment Network Embeddings: An Empirical Validation of Tinto's Student Integration Model	2021
Böttcher, A. <i>et al.</i>	A Data Science-Based Approach for Identifying Counseling Needs in First-Year Students	2021
Priyambada, S. A. <i>et al.</i>	Profile-Based Cluster Evolution Analysis: Identification of Migration Patterns for Understanding Student Learning Behavior	2021
Murshed, N. A.	A Fuzzy ARTMAP Framework for Predicting Student Dropout in Higher Education	2021
Suhaimi, N. A. D. <i>et al.</i>	Classification of Learner Retention Using Machine Learning Approaches	2021
Tenpipat, W. <i>et al.</i>	Student Dropout Prediction: A KMUTT Case Study	2020
Medina, E. C. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Model to Reduce the Dropout Rate of University Students in Peru: Bayesian Networks vs. Decision Trees	2020
Aguirre, C. E. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Data Analysis Techniques Applied to Dropping Out of University Studies	2020
Costa, A. G. <i>et al.</i>	Prediction Analysis of Student Dropout in a Computer Science Course Using Educational Data Mining	2020
Asha, P. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting University Dropout Through Data Analysis	2020
Bello, F. A. <i>et al.</i>	Using Machine Learning Methods to Identify Significant Variables for the Prediction of First-Year Informatics Engineering Students Dropout	2020
Figuerola-Cañas, J. <i>et al.</i>	Early Prediction of Dropout and Final Exam Performance in an Online Statistics Course	2020
Supic, H. <i>et al.</i>	Course-Specific Model for Prediction of At-Risk Students Based on Case-Based Reasoning	2020
Philippou, N. <i>et al.</i>	Using Machine Learning Techniques and Matric Grades to Predict the Success of First Year University Students	2020
Sa'ad, M. I. <i>et al.</i>	Student Prediction of Dropout Using Extreme Learning Machine (ELM) Algorithm	2020
Utari, M. <i>et al.</i>	Implementation of Data Mining for Dropout Prediction Using Random Forest Method	2020
Kiss, B. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Dropout Using High School and First-Semester Academic Achievement Measures	2019
Ortigosa, A. <i>et al.</i>	From Lab to Production: Lessons Learnt and Real-Life Challenges of an Early Student-Dropout Prevention System	2019
Jimenez, F. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting the Risk of Academic Dropout With Temporal Multi-Objective Optimization	2019
Sari, E. Y. <i>et al.</i>	Optimization of Weight Backpropagation With Particle Swarm Optimization for Student Dropout Prediction	2019
Oliveira, M. M. <i>et al.</i>	Understanding Student Dropout in Distance Learning	2019
Silva, P. M. <i>et al.</i>	Ensemble Regression Models Applied to Dropout in Higher Education	2019
Ahmed, S. A. <i>et al.</i>	A Machine Learning Approach to Predict Engineering Students at Risk of Dropout and Factors Behind: Bangladesh Perspective	2019
Mutrofin, S. <i>et al.</i>	Detection of Potentially Students Dropout of College in Case of Missing Value Using C4.5	2019
Naseem, M. <i>et al.</i>	Using Ensemble Decision Tree Model to Predict Student Dropout in Computing Science	2019
Tasnim, N. <i>et al.</i>	Identification of Dropout Students Using Educational Data Mining	2019
Hegde, V. <i>et al.</i>	Higher Education Student Dropout Prediction and Analysis Through Educational Data Mining	2018
Nagy, M. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Dropout in Higher Education Based on Secondary School Performance	2018
Solís, M. <i>et al.</i>	Perspectives to Predict Dropout in University Students With Machine Learning	2018
Perez, B. <i>et al.</i>	Applying Data Mining Techniques to Predict Student Dropout: A Case Study	2018
Limsathitwong, K. <i>et al.</i>	Dropout Prediction System to Reduce Discontinue Study Rate of Information Technology Students	2018
Mayra, A. <i>et al.</i>	Factors to Predict Dropout at the Universities: A Case of Study in Ecuador	2018
Kuo, J. Y. <i>et al.</i>	Using Stacked Denoising Autoencoder for the Student Dropout Prediction	2017
Kostopoulos, G. <i>et al.</i>	Early Dropout Prediction in Distance Higher Education Using Active Learning	2017
Gopalakrishnan, A. <i>et al.</i>	A Multifaceted Data Mining Approach to Understanding What Factors Lead College Students to Persist and Graduate	2017
de la Peña, D. <i>et al.</i>	Mining Activity Grades to Model Students' Performance	2017
Camba, J. <i>et al.</i>	Student Analytics Using Support Vector Machines	2016
Pokrajac, D. D. <i>et al.</i>	Prediction of Retention at Historically Black College/University Using Artificial Neural Networks	2016
de Almeida Neto, F. A. <i>et al.</i>	Elicited and Mined Rules for Dropout Prevention in Online Courses	2015
Dewan, M. A. A. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Dropout-Prone Students in E-Learning Education System	2015

Table 7: List of Publications Included in the SLR (Proquest)

Authors	Title / <i>Free translation into English, when applicable</i>	Year
El Mahmoudi, A. <i>et al.</i>	Predictive Analytics Leveraging a Machine Learning Approach to Identify Students' Reasons for Dropping out of University	2025
Reina Marín, Y. <i>et al.</i>	Data Mining to Identify University Student Dropout Factors	2025
Carballo-Mendivil, B. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Student Dropout from Day One: XGBoost-Based Early Warning System Using Pre-Enrollment Data	2025
Romero, S. and Liao, X.	Statistical and machine learning models for predicting university dropout and scholarship impact	2025
Crisp, E. <i>et al.</i>	A model for predicting student nurse attrition during pre-registration training: A retrospective observations study using routinely collected administrative data	2025
Hassan, S. <i>et al.</i>	Integrating cGAN-Enhanced Prediction with Hybrid Intervention Recommendations Systems for Student Dropout Prevention	2025
Marcolino, M. <i>et al.</i>	Student dropout prediction through machine learning optimization: insights from moodle log data	2025
Bettahi, A. <i>et al.</i>	A Modular and Explainable Machine Learning Pipeline for Student Dropout Prediction in Higher Education	2025
Liu, H. <i>et al.</i>	Model interpretability on private-safe oriented student dropout prediction	2025
Jain, A. <i>et al.</i>	A PSO weighted ensemble framework with SMOTE balancing for student dropout prediction in smart education systems	2025
Na, J. <i>et al.</i>	A Study on Exploiting Temporal Patterns in Semester Records for Efficient Student Dropout Prediction	2025
Villar, A. and Velini, C.	Supervised machine learning algorithms for predicting student dropout and academic success: a comparative study	2024
Salaberri, P. <i>et al.</i>	Educational Data Mining for Dropout Prediction: an Experience at a University in Southern Brazil	2024
Kim, S. <i>et al.</i>	Why Do Students Drop Out? University Dropout Prediction and Associated Factor Analysis Using Machine Learning Techniques	2023
Barros, B. <i>et al.</i>	Evaluating Splitting Approaches in the Context of Student Dropout Prediction	2019
Marina, B. and Senthilrajan, A.	HFIPO-DPNN: A Framework for Predicting the Dropout of Physically Impaired Student from Education	2023
Cho, C. <i>et al.</i>	A Study on Dropout Prediction for University Students Using Machine Learning	2023
Hyun-Sik, W. <i>et al.</i>	University Student Dropout Prediction Using Pretrained Language Models	2023
Kim, S. <i>et al.</i>	Student Dropout Prediction for University with High Precision and Recall	2023
Martins, M. <i>et al.</i>	Multi-Class Phased Prediction of Academic Performance and Dropout in Higher Education	2023
Song, Z. <i>et al.</i>	All-Year Dropout Prediction Modeling and Analysis for University Students	2023
Segura, M. <i>et al.</i>	Machine Learning Prediction of University Student Dropout: Does Preference Play a Key Role?	2022
Flores, V. <i>et al.</i>	Comparison of Predictive Models with Balanced Classes Using the SMOTE Method for the Forecast of Student Dropout in Higher Education	2022
Buchhorn, J. and Wigger, B.	Predicting Student Dropout: A Replication Study Based on Neural Networks	2021
Kabathova, J. and Drlik, M.	Towards Predicting Student's Dropout in University Courses Using Different Machine Learning Techniques	2021
Martins, M. <i>et al.</i>	Previsão do abandono acadêmico numa instituição de ensino superior com recurso a data mining / <i>Prediction of academic dropout in a higher education institution using data mining</i>	2020
Wan, Y. <i>et al.</i>	Predicting Student Drop-Out in Higher Institution Using Data Mining Techniques	2020
Urbina-Nájera, A. <i>et al.</i>	University dropout: Patterns to prevent it by applying educational data mining	2020
Bedregal-Alpaca, N. <i>et al.</i>	Classification Models for Determining Types of Academic Risk and Predicting Dropout in University Students	2020
Sani, N. <i>et al.</i>	Drop-Out Prediction in Higher Education Among B40 Students	2020
Berens, J. <i>et al.</i>	Early Detection of Students at Risk – Predicting Student Dropouts Using Administrative Student Data and Machine Learning Methods	2018
Tan, M. and Shao, P.	Prediction of Student Dropout in E-Learning Program Through the Use of Machine Learning Method	2015